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RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SCHOOL ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND TEACHERS' TASK PERFORMANCE IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the relationship between school organizational culture and teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. It adopted a correlation survey research design. Three research questions guided the study and one hypothesis was tested. The population for the study is 6,396 teachers in the 261 state government-owned secondary schools in Anambra State. A sample of 1,280 teachers composed using proportionate stratified and simple random sampling techniques was involved in the study. Two researchers developed instruments namely School Organizational Culture Questionnaire (SOCQ) and the Teachers' Task Performance Questionnaire (TTPQ) used for data collection. The instruments were validated by three experts. The internal consistency method was used to determine the reliability of the instruments and this yielded Cronbach Alpha coefficient values of 0.84 and 0.70 for the two instruments respectively. The researchers with the aid of three research assistants collected data. Out of 1,280 copies of each of the questionnaires administered to the respondents, 1256 copies representing 98% were successfully completed, retrieved, and used for data analysis. The research questions were answered using aggregate scores, while the hypothesis was tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation at a 0.05 level of significance. The results of the findings include among others that the majority of the teachers in the State perceived their school organizational culture and their task performance as good and that there is a low positive relationship between teachers' perceived school organizational culture and their task performance. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that the State School Management Board should organize workshops, seminars, and conferences aimed at exposing teachers to the importance of good organizational culture in schools. This will enable both the principals and teachers to know what is expected of them and how to go about fostering positive types of cultures in their schools. Conclusions were made and implications of the findings were also drawn.

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Introduction

Schools possess an organizational culture and the dynamism of this culture vary from one school to another. It is the principal's responsibility to uphold and develop the school's culture in a given direction through actions and deeds as well as management style. Every organization is affected by its culture and every organization has a culture (Thompson, 2021). Also, formal organizations like schools, have various set guidelines which usually help the employees to work willingly and accordingly in the workplace. It is widely believed that the effectiveness of a school, achievement of its tasks and set objectives are to a large extent dependent on the level of effort put in by each member of the workforce as well as the school's organizational culture (Berg, 2009). Every organization has its unique style of working which contributes to form the organizational culture. Koontz and O' Donnell (2011) asserted that culture is the general pattern of behaviour, shared beliefs and values that members of an organization have in common. In education, it involves the transmitting of knowledge, beliefs and patterns of behaviour over a period of time. Thus organizational culture is therefore fundamentally made up of the beliefs, norms, ideologies, principles and values of such an organization. The issue of organizational culture in schools stems from the meeting of these two areas, one more focused on the practice of management, the other on understanding these practices (Torres, 2022). Since the school is an organization, it therefore means that the culture of any school could influence the people within the school. Lunenburg and Orstein (2012) affirmed this when they stated that the effectiveness of the school as a formal organization is influenced by the school culture.

The term **school culture** generally refers to the beliefs, perceptions, relationships, attitudes and written rules that shape and influence every aspect of how a school functions. Schein (2011) opined that school culture refers to the deep patterns of values, beliefs, and traditions that have been formed over the course of the school's history which are understood by members of the school community. Continuing, Schein asserted that school culture is built within the school overtime, as teachers, principals, parents and students work together. It is therefore likely that school culture often influences the way teachers perform their duties and also their professional growth which takes place within the school.

The culture of a school decides the way teachers interact amongst themselves and perform their duties. Different schools operate different cultures and it is essential for employees, subordinates and super-ordinates alike to adjust well to their respective school's culture to enjoy their work and ensure optimum proficiency. In line with this view is Unachukwu (1999) that every school should have certain values, policies and guidelines which differentiate it from others. The principles and values of such schools form the school's culture. In a school environment characterized by a positive school culture, most of the teachers share common beliefs, values and behaviour that show the way in which the school should be run. Much of what happens in such schools, including the ways in which the schools are managed and administered is likely to be influenced by the culture that has evolved in the school overtime. It therefore seems that there is a link between the culture of a school and its performance.

Collaborating this, Groysberg, Lee, Price & Cheng (2018) posited that organizational culture has a lot to do with the collective effect of the common beliefs, behaviours, and values of the people within an organization. Those norms within any organization regulate how their employees perform, how they co-operate with each other, whether they feel motivated to meet goals, and if they are sincerely into the organization's overall mission. Furthermore, it exposes how employees get their work done either independently or collaboratively. It also emphasizes on if employees feel inspired, committed, and engaged, or annoyed, overworked, and underappreciated in the course of carrying out their assigned tasks?

An earlier author named Hampden-Turner (1990) prescribed a multi-dimensional approach to understanding the attributes and situational contexts of school culture. According to the author, four types of organizational culture are mostly prevalent in schools and they include: role culture, collegial culture, atomistic culture and power culture. It is important to note that not all cultures operating in schools can foster the growth and proper development of the school. In view of this, it is important to briefly introduce the various types of culture that can be seen in most secondary schools. One of such and which is adopted in this study is the classification by Hampden-Turner (1990) which was also supported by Thompson (2000).

Role culture is a culture where every teacher is delegated roles and responsibilities according to his area of specialization, educational qualification and interests in order to extract the best out of him. Schools that practice role culture stress the need for teachers to perform their roles creditably and teachers are held solely

responsible for the roles assigned to them. Teachers in such schools carry out their teaching roles, delegated tasks and other responsibilities with trust and there is autonomy in each person's role.

In the collegial culture, there is recognition of achievements, exchange of ideas, involvement of teachers in decision making, celebration of achievements and open communication among teachers. Each teacher in the school is encouraged to reach his or her highest potential. In such schools, teams are formed to solve particular problems and produce results. Contributing on this, Mitchell and Sackney (2006) opined that in the collegial culture emphasis is on high levels of teamwork and productivity.

The atomistic culture is alternatively referred to as person/ support culture. The culture is formed where all individuals believe themselves to be superior to the school organization. Teachers operating this culture, are more concerned about their own self and how to better their lot rather than the corporate goals of the school.

In some schools power is in the hands of only a few people and only those few are authorized to take decisions. These few are the ones who enjoy special privileges in the school. They are the most important people at the workplace and also the major decision makers. In such a culture teachers have no option than to strictly follow their principal's instruction. This type of school culture is known as power culture. Writing on this, Handy (2003) asserted that in power culture, the principals are dedicated towards ensuring that teachers perform their duties as and when due; they expect people to do what they are told without delay or debate. If principals get this culture right, it can result in a happy and satisfactory school environment that in turn breeds intense commitment of teachers to the corporate goals of the school. However, operating it wrongly can lead to a high staff turnover as well as a general lack of effort and enthusiasm on the part of the teachers in the school.

Kahler (2006) asserted that one of the fundamental concerns of the school as an organization is the effectiveness and improvement of the teaching and learning process. Teachers are a very important facet of any society and are also the bedrock of the educational system because they play a vital role in the attainment of goals in education and also the nation at large. They are the ones responsible for high standards in education, transmission of norms and national values in their pupils by teaching them as well as being good models to them (Mgbere& Andrew, 2019).

Continuing, Mgbere and Andrew (2019) stated that teacher performance is defined as the sum total of a teacher's execution of assigned tasks. The success and quality of the school organization is closely tied to the job performance of each teacher and this success is greatly dependent on the quality of the teachers and their performance level in terms of professional qualification, teaching experience, knowledge of subject matter and quality of students produced which is (output). Earlier author Kahler(2006) elaborated that teacher's task performance include aspects of curriculum delivery (teachers are expected to plan, implement and evaluate their lessons); participation in extra-curricular activities (being in school on time for morning assembly, participation in sports, disciplining students, rendering of support services by teachers among others) and professional development (taking part in professional organizational life, reading professional write-ups, attending professional lectures aimed at staff training) and all other activities that continuously enhance the teachers' task performance.

From literature and visits to some public secondary schools in Anambra State, the researchers observed that irrespective of the fact that the task of teaching demands competence, dedication, consistency and efficiency, many teachers in secondary schools in the State seem to have failed in this call to duty. Some teachers seem to display acts of unseriousness, lack of dedication to their task performance and inconsistency. Maduewesi (2005) observed that many teachers in Anambra State appear to be unprepared in the performance of their task and end up manifesting poor teaching skills, inefficient school administration and these ultimately affect the proper growth and development of the school. Umejih (2005) further noted that there is a rise in cases of declining morale and discipline amongst teachers in Anambra State. Umejih also noted that this general decline in the task performance of teachers has led to a lower perception of public secondary schools in Anambra State by most parents. Obanya (2008) in agreement noted that the amount of learning and knowledge imparted in some public secondary schools in Anambra State is scanty and poor and alluded it this to challenges faced by teachers.

These challenges seem traceable to school culture and poor administration. According to Uzoehina (2014) these challenges among others include: indiscipline such as: lateness and outright non-attendance to classes, poor preparation of lessons, poor delivery of lessons, non- involvement in extra-curricular activities in the school, lack of enthusiasm in continuous professional development, of which affect teacher's task performance. This seeming ineffectiveness of teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State has greatly attracted public attention and criticisms against teachers as not being committed to their duties. With all these complaints comes the need to ensure that secondary schools in Anambra State should have laid down contexts within which the school operates with greater emphasis on their set norms, standards, principles and values.

However, not all public secondary schools in Anambra State are in this dilemma since they all differ in their cultural norms and the levels of teachers' task performance. In some of the public secondary schools, there appear to be consistency, efficiency and dedication to duty, cordiality among teachers, high school tone, discipline and trust, whereas in some others, the reverse seems to be the case. It is therefore possible that these differences in the levels of task performance of teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State may be as a result of differences in the nature and type of school culture being operated. It is this worrisome situation that urged the researchers to embark on this study which sought answer to the question: Is there a relationship between school organizational culture and teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the perceived school organizational culture scores of teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What are the task performance scores of teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
3. What is the nature of the relationship existing between teachers' perceived school organizational culture and their task performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

This hypotheses was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship between teachers' perceived school organizational culture scores and their task performance scores in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Method

The study employed the correlation survey research design and was carried out in Anambra State. The population of the study is 6,396 teachers in the 261 public secondary schools in the six education zones in the state. The sample for this study is 1,280 respondents drawn from the population of the study using proportionate stratified and simple random sampling technique. The sample is 20% of the population. Two researchers developed questionnaires titled "School Organizational Culture Questionnaire" (SOCQ) and "Teachers' Task Performance Questionnaire" (TTPQ) were used for data collection. The school organizational culture questionnaire was divided into two sections, A and B. Section A sought information on the personal data of respondents while section B which contains 32 items sought information on school organizational culture operating in the schools. The second questionnaire tagged: "Teachers' Task Performance Questionnaire" (TTPQ) contains a total of 22 items on the various variables of teachers' task performance. Both questionnaires were structured on a four-point response scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD), weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The instruments were subjected to face validation using three experts who are lecturers, from the Department of Educational Management and Policy and the other in Educational Measurement and Evaluation in the Department of Educational Foundations, all in the Faculty of Education, NnamdiAzikiwe University. The internal consistency of the questionnaires was determined using 50 teachers in two secondary schools in Enugu State. The test yielded Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficients of 0.80 and 0.70 for SOCQ and TTPQ respectively.

The researchers together with three research assistants collected data for the study using the direct method of administration and retrieval of the questionnaire. Out of 1,280 copies of each of the questionnaires administered, 1,256 of each representing 98% were properly completed, successfully retrieved and used for data analysis. Research questions one and two were analyzed using aggregate scores while Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was applied in answering research questions three and to test the null hypotheses at 0.05

level of significance. The Correlation coefficient was interpreted using the rule posited by Nworgu (2015) that: 0.80 and above (negative or positive) = very high relationship, 0.60 to 0.80 (negative or positive) = high relationship, 0.40 to 0.60 (negative or positive) = medium relationship, 0.20 to 0.40 (negative or positive) = low relationship, 0.00 to 0.20 (negative or positive) = very low or no relationship. The calculated r was then compared with the stipulated level of significance (0.05) and degree of freedom such that, the null hypotheses was not accepted where the stipulated r value is greater than the tabulated r at the level of significance and degree of freedom, the null hypothesis was not accepted but if otherwise it was accepted.

Results: The results are presented in tables according to the Research questions and hypotheses.

Research Question 1

What are the teachers' perceived school organizational culture scores in public secondary schools in Anambra state?

Table 1: Range of scores of teachers' on their perceived school organizational culture

Types of SOC	Range of scores	N	%	Remarks
ROLE	12-29	294	23.4	Poor org. culture
	30-48	962	96.6	Good org. culture
COLLEGIAL	6-14	136	10.8	Poor org. culture
	15-24	1120	89.2	Good org. culture
ATOMISTIC	7 -17	264	21.0	Poor.org. culture
	18-28	992	79.0	Good org. culture
POWER	7-17	477	38.0	Poor. org. culture
	18-28	779	62.0	Good org. culture
Sch. org. culture	32-79	188	15.0	Poor org. culture
	80-128	1068	85.0	Good org. culture

Results from Table 1 revealed that teachers perceived that the four types of organizational culture were obtained in secondary schools in Anambra State. The analysis further show that 1068 (85.0%) of the teachers with scores ranging from 80 to 128 perceived their school organizational culture to be good, while 188 (15.0%) who scored between 32 and 79 perceived their school organizational culture to be poor. Also, Table 1 revealed that the teachers believed that all the four types of the school organizational culture are in their schools.

Research Question 2

What are the task performance scores of secondary school teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra state?

Table 2: Range of scores of teachers' task performance

Range of scores	N	%	Remarks
22 – 54	92	7.3	Poor task performance
55 – 88	1164	92.7	Good task performance

Data on Table 2 revealed that 1164 (92.7%) of the teachers with scores ranging from 55 to 88 have good task performance, while 92 (7.3%) teachers who scored between 22 and 54 have poor task performance.

Research Question 3

What relationship exists between the teachers' perceived school organizational culture and their task performance in secondary schools?

Table 3: Pearson r on teachers'perceived school organizational culture and their task performance

Source of Variation	N	Org. Culture r	Task Performance r	Remark
Org. Culture	1256	1.00	0.27	LowPositive Relationship
Task performance	1256	0.27	1.00	

Table 3 reveals that there is low positive relationship $r = 0.27$ existing between the teachers' perceived school organizational culture and their task performance in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Testing the Null Hypotheses

There is no significant relationship existing between the teachers'perceived school organizational culture and their task performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: Significance of Pearson r on the teachers' school organizational culture and their task performance using probability table of r.

N	cal. r	df	crit. r	Remark
1256	0.27	1254	0.19	Significant

Table 4 indicates that at 0.05 level of significance and 1254 df, the calculated r 0.27 is greater than the critical r 0.19. Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that the relationship existing between the teachers'school organizational culture and their task performance in secondary schools is significant.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study, revealed that from the perception of teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State that the various types of school organizational culture such as the role culture, atomistic culture, collegial culture and power culture were practiced in their schools. The findings further revealed that the majority of the schools practice more of role culture followed closely by collegial culture, then atomistic culture and finally power culture. This is in line with the view of Hampden-Turner (1990) who asserted that the four types of organizational culture are mostly prevalent in schools and in the following order: role, collegial, atomistic and power culture. Furthermore, the findings revealed that majority of teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State perceive their school organizational culture to be good whereas a minority perceive their school organizational culture as poor.This is in line with Lunenburg and Orstein (2012) who agreed that the effectiveness of the school as a formal organisation is greatly influenced by the school culture.

The findings of this study also indicated that majority of the teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State, perceive their task performance as good while others whose range of scores were less, perceived their task performance as poor. The findings differ from the assertions of scholars Maduwesi (2005), Umejih (2005) and Obanya (2008) who suggested that the teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State have poor task performance. The difference in the findings of this present study from the assertions of earlier scholars could be because these studies were the happenings as at the time; and the findings of the present study reveals that things must have changed overtime and improved for the better. Again, perhaps the public secondary schools in Anambra State as at the time of carrying out the previous studies may have been practicing negative organizational cultures which also negatively influenced their level of task performance. Probably within the time difference of approximately nine years from the date of the last study much effect may have been put in the area of study in relation to improvements in school culture.

The findings of this study show that there is a low positive relationship existing between the teachers' perceived school organizational culture and their task performance. The relationship was also found to be

significant. From these findings, it can be deduced that school organizational culture is actually a positive predictor for teacher task performance although it is low. This is supported by Efanga and Ifejiagwa (2014) who reported that there is a significant relationship between teachers' perception of their organizational culture and performance in secondary schools in AkwaIbom State, Nigeria. This finding however, contradicts Ahmad (2013) who found out that the relationship between school organizational culture and teacher task performance has no direct effect against teachers' performance. This contradiction could be attributed to difference in time and geographical location. The study by Efanga and Ifejiagwa was carried out in the year 2014 whereas the present study was carried out in the year 2016. This implies that the differences in time and geographical locations of conducting both studies could have influenced the findings of both studies.

Conclusion

From the findings of this study it could be inferred that the majority of the teachers in secondary schools in Anambra State perceive their school organizational culture and their task performance to be good. The findings further concluded that there is also a significantly low positive relationship between male and female teachers' perception of the relationship existing between their school organizational culture and their task performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researchers made the following recommendations:

1. The government and management board of schools, should regularly organize workshops, seminars and conferences aimed at revealing the importance of fostering good organizational culture in schools. This will enable both the principals and their teachers to know what is expected of them to do and how to go about inculcating and fostering the positive types of cultures in their schools.
2. Teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra state should be encouraged by their principals to identify the positive cultures being practiced in their schools and let go of the negative ones.
3. Educational policy makers should ensure that positive types of culture are inculcated and enshrined in the policy making process. They should further endeavour to ensure that the formulated policies are being adhered to by all the public secondary schools in Anambra State.

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